

POPULATION EMPLOYMENT AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. The job market is being transformed by artificial intelligence (AI), which has emerged as a revolutionary technology. Understanding how AI will impact employment and the future of work is critical. The purpose of this article is to explore the many impacts of AI on the labor market, including job creation, skill needs, job displacement, and potential legislative outcomes.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Economic growth, Smart economy, Labor market, Robotization of labor.

Currently, on a global scale, digital technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of things (Internet of things), big data (Big Data) are rapidly entering all fields. The widespread introduction of cyber-physical systems to the organization and service of production and human needs, including life, work and leisure, is called the fourth industrial revolution. A number of experts look at this as a challenge and emphasize that everyone in the society should have an understanding of digital technologies and be able to use them effectively, which is the main element of economic development.

In accordance with the generally accepted approach, to date, humanity has experienced 3 industrial revolutions:

- 1) the beginning of the use of hydraulics to mechanize production;
- 2) use of electricity;
- 3) introduction of electronics for production automation¹.

Artificial intelligence, combined with robotics and advanced online technologies, already today effectively copes with many tasks that previously could only be performed by people. For example, AI has already been actively introduced into the field of medicine, where smart programs help make diagnoses and select treatment methods. AI is also used in journalism, online education, recruitment, real-time translation functions. And in general, modern digital technologies are capable of implementing or significantly simplifying many processes.

But at the same time, the rapid development of AI has highlighted the fact that, while machines help people solve their problems, they will also create new problems that will affect the economic, legal and ethical foundations of our society.

In many industries, manufacturing and services, there is already a shortage of professionally trained specialists. Google, Facebook, Apple, Amazon, Uber and other big tech companies are willing to pay millions of dollars for AI experts who urgently need talent to work on facial recognition, digital assistants and self-driving vehicles.

According to research by the World Economic Forum (WEF), technology will be one of the main factors affecting business in the next five years. The overwhelming majority (75%) of the organizations that participated in the survey indicated that they are committed to the widespread use of big data, cloud computing and artificial intelligence technologies.

¹ Savchuk T. Threats from the future: can robots completely replace humans? URL: <https://ru.krymr.com/a/28676115.html> (дата обращения: 20.10.2020).

The Fourth Industrial Revolution has accelerated the pace of adoption of technologies and shifted the frontier between humans and machines across sectors and geographies. Technology is altering the way we work, but also changing job content, skills in need, and which jobs are being displaced. Understanding how technologies will impact labour markets is crucial for determining whether people will be able to transition from declining occupations to the jobs of tomorrow.

The fastest-growing jobs support sales growth and customer engagement, the search for talent, and technology/IT. Research conducted by LinkedIn for the Future of Jobs Report 2023 describes the 100 roles that have grown fastest, consistently and globally, over the last four years – known as the “Jobs on the Rise”. While ILO and OECD data show which sectors are employing more people, Jobs on the Rise data identifies the specific job types that have experienced significant growth. Figure B.1 organizes the 100 Jobs on the Rise into broad types.

Fig. 1² LinkedIn jobs on the rise, 2018-2022. Growing roles by job type.

Conclusion

Let us summarize and outline the main expected positive and negative consequences of robotization and production automation on the labor market:

- 1) growth in labor productivity;
- 2) increasing demand for specialists with high-tech knowledge and skills;
- 3) uneven implementation of automation processes in sectors of the national economy, incl. h. taking into account territorial socio-economic characteristics;
- 4) the disappearance of some professions, the emergence of new ones;
- 5) loss of jobs and, probably, an increase in the importance of measures taken by the authorities in response to this.

To fill the shortage of highly qualified specialists in the field of AI, it is necessary to develop modern models and systems for personnel training. Several approaches can be proposed for this:

² Source World Economic Forum, LinkedIn.

- funding from the state of higher educational institutions in terms of creating new scientific directions for the implementation of training programs for specialists in the field of digital technologies;
- creation of programs for professional retraining of personnel to train them on the job;
- in state and municipal structures, at manufacturing enterprises, in the field of large and medium-sized businesses, apply a system of training specialists independently by introducing their own AI educational programs in the field of activity.

To minimize negative social consequences on the part of the government, the following measures will be optimal:

- expanding government control and investment in the field of AI;
- improving the state system of education and training with an emphasis on the most in-demand specialties;
- adaptation of the legal framework and social security system to the conditions of growing numbers of unemployed and increasing inequality in the level of income of the population.

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